

THE WAYS OF USING NATURAL RESOURCES CAREFULLY IN SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article deals with some issues of the formation of initial concepts of saving electricity in children of preschool age. The author emphasizes that the skills formed in children will be of decisive importance throughout their lives.*

Keywords: *electricity, preschool education, methodology, savings.*

In the nature of Uzbekistan, there are enough resources that help a child get the necessary knowledge and impressions. Interest in inanimate and especially living nature objects around exists in children early. The child becomes more interested in what he sees with his eyes. Children try to see and touch everything with their own eyes.

While supporting children's interest in the environment, it should not be forgotten that they should be educated in the spirit of nature conservation. To make the children of preschool educational institutions feel the responsibility of rational use of natural resources, to acquire knowledge in the field of nature protection, respect for the nature of our country, the environment, careful attitude and a sense of responsibility towards it. We must educate every child of preschool age to use with.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-628 dated July 14, 2020, a decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on increasing energy efficiency in our country, introducing energy-saving technologies and developing renewable energy sources was adopted. The results of the study carried out in the form of control-analysis of this Law in the regions, an effective system of monitoring the consumption efficiency of energy resources, the lack of services for the introduction of modern energy-saving technologies, and the low level of use of information and communication technologies in this area have been shown.

One of the most important issues is to organize systematic and targeted promotional events on the basis of a plan and schedule to explain the content, nature and significance of this Law to the public, paying special attention to the use of television and radio opportunities, and at the same time, forming the skills of careful use of natural resources in pre-school education.

First, children are full-fledged consumers of electricity, like adults. Secondly, a child who has learned to use electricity carefully and sparingly is more likely to maintain this approach throughout life. Thirdly, learning the physical properties of electricity at the level of safety is not without benefits for children.

There are opportunities to explain cases like the following to children through certain methods.

Energy crises and price fluctuations are pushing many people to use electricity sparingly. To reduce these costs, first of all, it is necessary to clarify the question of what "eats up" the most electricity in our home, and if necessary, to change some of our habits.

Experts of the French Schneider Electric energy management company have compiled a list of the most energy-consuming appliances in households. In this list, heating and cooling equipment took the first place - they account for 50-70 percent of the total consumption.

"Large appliances such as air conditioners and vacuum cleaners take up a large part of household electricity consumption. The electricity consumption of such equipment can be 50-70% of the total consumption. This depends on whether the unit is a heating or cooling unit. Heating equipment requires much more energy than cooling equipment," says the company's engineer Andryus Peryavichyus.

According to him, water heaters (boilers) are the second most energy-consuming equipment. If the water heated in the boiler is used for washing, washing dishes, washing clothes, the contribution of these costs can reach up to 12% of the annual consumption. Consumption indicators of an electric water heater are closely related to the number of family members and their thrift culture. In some cases, it reaches up to 400 kilowatt-hours per month.

The consumption of such equipment can be reduced only through strict control. For example, you can turn on the "vacation" mode when you are not at home for a long time. It is also possible to turn off the boiler during the hours when no one is using the water.

On average, a washing machine accounts for 2–5% of annual consumption, a dishwasher for 2–3%, and an electric stove and oven for 8%. Naturally, the consumption of these electrical appliances depends on how much we use them. It has been proven that energy consumption can be significantly reduced by using only full loads of washing machines and dishwashers.

"Computers, televisions, gadgets are also very popular today and consume about 10 percent of our total expenses." These devices are usually left connected to the home network and receive current even when they are not turned on," says A. Peryavichyus.

According to average statistics, about 10-12% of the total costs are spent on lighting our home. If solid-state lamps are used instead of light-emitting diode lamps, this indicator can be several times higher. When it comes to lighting, the simplest way to save electricity is to not leave lights on in rooms when no one needs them.

A standard refrigerator consumes an average of 150 kilowatt-hours of energy per year. However, experts say that if the refrigerator is placed too close to the wall or corner of the room and if the air circulation is not good, if it is in a very hot room, the energy consumption will increase. "Another aspect is that the refrigerator works efficiently when it is 3/4 full. "For this reason, it should not be filled with old things," says A.Peryavichyus.

In conclusion, most energy efficient solutions in the home and office can be implemented quickly and easily. It does not require special investment or hard work. First of all, we need to audit our home (or office) from time to time. Everyone, regardless of today's consumption figure, will find some surplus to save.

One more aspect should not be forgotten here. There is a theory in science called "Behavioral Economics" (one of its founders, Richard Thaler, was awarded the Nobel Prize in 2017). According to this theory, people sometimes take economically irrational actions that are contrary to their behavior. For example, he buys a subscription to a fitness club, but does not go.

It is this economic model that can be effectively used in forming the skills to be economical and responsible in the use of energy and water resources, and at least to strictly control one's own consumption. A simple example: if, along with the usual dry statistical information about the monthly electricity consumption that comes to your phone every month, it will be shown that this household used more/less than the average consumption in its neighborhood, district and republic in a month, this information will make anyone think, "rein" their consumption. will be a very strong impulse.

As can be seen from the above, there are opportunities to explain to children how to use electricity wisely, sparingly and sparingly. For example, it will be necessary to provide information about electricity, which is a complex physical phenomenon. In this case, it is possible to explain the creation of electricity from positive and negative charges, along with its beneficial aspects, which can put an end to a person's life due to improper use, organizing a stimulating situation using visual weapons.

Also, it will be necessary to explain that electricity is a commodity, therefore it can be produced and sold, and every consumer can buy it. In this case, one kilowatt-hour of energy can be compared to an apple or a cookie, as an example of an air conditioner that burns for one hour. This shows that electricity is a certain amount of money and a valuable product.

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